

The Effect of Assets Structure, Capital Structure, Company Size, Macro Economy, Risk Management, and Profitability on The Value of The Firm with Good Corporate Governance as Variable Moderating in Leasing Company on Indonesia Stock Exchange

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Ignatius Kurniawan * ⁽²⁾Tri Ratnawati ⁽³⁾Srie Hartutie Moehaditoyo

Correspondence email address: ignatiuskurniawan96@gmail.com

⁽¹⁾ ⁽²⁾ ⁽³⁾Economics and Business, August 17, 1945 Surabaya University, Indonesia

Abstract

This study aims to discuss the effect of Assets Structure, Capital Structure, Company Size, Macro Economy, Risk Management, and Profitability on The Value of the Firm Leasing Company on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, with moderating variables Good Corporate Governance. Secondary data was collected from financial companies' financial statements listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2013 to 2018, secondary data was also obtained from the Indonesia Stock Exchange website, Bank Indonesia website and the Central Statistics Agency website. The results showed the coefficient of determination test obtained the number 0.670, which means the variables used in the study are the Asset Structure, Capital Structure, Company Size, Macroeconomics, Risk Management, Profitability, and Corporate Governance can affect the variable Company Value of 67.0%. Corporate governance as a moderator variable has a negative and significant effect.

Keywords: *Assets Structure, Company Size, Macro Economy, Value of The Firm, Leasing Company, Indonesia Stock Exchange*

1. Introduction

Good economic growth and a very large number of productive age populations are in need of transportation facilities that support the mobilization of citizens to move quickly and easily. The lack of public transportation services is the reason people choose to buy motorbikes and cars rather than using public transportation. Such a situation is driving the fertile growth of finance companies in Indonesia. Based on the type of activity, finance companies have the largest receivables compared to other types of activities. This can be seen in the graph below, where from 2013 - 2018, receivables from multi finance companies accounted for 60% of the total receivables from financial institutions and continued to show graphs increasing each year. This condition shows that the company's finance market share is still growing considering the high demand for motor vehicles.

So that finance companies can continue to survive, it needs management who is able to manage the company well. The Financial Services Authority (OJK) as a government representative in supervisors and supervisors of finance companies applies strict rules to the company's operational activities with the aim that the business can run well by observing the limitations set out in the law. The high demand for vehicles is accompanied by an increase in per capita income of the population, the opportunity to earn profits from finance companies and various benefits if the company goes public does not make all finance companies immediately jump into the stock market by selling the company's shares. Of the 185 finance companies listed on the Indonesian Financial Services Association, only 14 companies have sold shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. This condition raises a phenomenon and is interesting for further research.

It is important for companies to be skilled at maintaining the performance of their companies in order to remain high-value so that potential investors are willing to pay the price offered if the financing company is sold then the value of the company must be proportional to the price offered. Because potential investors want their prosperity to increase after buying the company (Brigham and Gapenski, 1996). Company value is the actual value per share that will be received if the company's assets are sold at stock prices (Gitman, 2006). Research on Asset Structure for Company Value. Brigham and Gapenski (1996) stated that in general companies that have large guarantees will be more trusted by investors to invest their capital. Brealey and Myers (2009) state that capital structure is a combination of debt and capital. An optimal capital structure can optimize the company's market value. Research on macroeconomic relations and risk management.

Banks whose main function is mediation are very vulnerable to inflation risks associated with the mobilization of funds (Rivai, 2009).

The difference between the real exchange rate and the nominal exchange rate is important to understand because both have different effects on exchange rate risk. Fainstein and Novikov (2011) stated that bad loans were significantly caused by changes in real GDP, meaning that an increase in fast loan growth proves that bank credit risk management policies ignore changes in macroeconomic variables during the analysis period. This study will try to analyze the effect of the Asset Structure, Capital Structure, Company Size, Macroeconomics, Risk Management and Profitability on Company Value with Good Corporate Governance (GCG), as a Moderation Variable. The renewal of this research is to develop GCG variables moderating risk management to the value of the firm and GCG moderating profitability to the value of the firm. It is hoped that this research can contribute to scientific knowledge in the economy, especially in the management of finance companies to be able to compete and have good prospects in the future. This research is also expected to provide input for the Financial Services Authority (OJK) in the supervision and management of finance companies to comply with the principles of good corporate governance.

2. Literature Review

Financial management consists of planning activities, analyzing financial activities as well as controlling or controlling financial activities. Although financial management varies from one company to another, all of them have the same rationale. Weston and Copeland (1999) state that financial management is one of the functional management fields in a company, which learns about the use of funds, how to obtain funds and how to share the results of a company's operations. Financial management mainly deals with money management issues. Furthermore, Ross, Westerfield, and Jordan (2009) stated that corporate financial management is a study of how to allocate long-term investments that are profitable for the company, how to get long-term funding to finance investments, and how to manage the company's daily financial activities. Financial statement analysis is the application of analytical tools and techniques for general purpose financial statements and related data to produce useful estimates and conclusions in business analysis. Analysis of financial statements needs to be done carefully by using the right analytical methods and techniques so that the expected results are truly correct.

According to Brigham and Houston (2006) companies that have adequate assets or assets that have a greater ratio of long-term fixed assets will use more long-term debt because existing fixed assets can be used as collateral for the debt. So it can be said that the structure of assets can be used to determine how much long-term debt can be taken and this will affect the determination of the size of the capital structure. The composition of assets that can be used as collateral for a company affects its financing and an investor will more easily provide loans if accompanied by existing collateral. According to Brealey and Myers (2009), a company's capital structure is centered on a combination of debt and capital. The choice of capital structure is fundamentally a marketing problem. Further explained, the company can issue several different shares with various combinations. But the company also tries to find combinations that can optimize market value. An optimal capital structure is one thing that can maximize the market value of the company's outstanding shares. If this ideal combination can be created, the company's shares will reach the highest price and the capital structure used is the optimal capital structure.

Funding decisions (capital structure) will involve determining the optimal combination of the use of various sources of funds which basically can be divided into two, 1) relating to external funding because it will lead to decision making regarding capital structure, which will determine the proportion between long-term debt and own capital. This is evident in the company's debt to equity ratio. 2) related to internal funding, the application is the determination of dividend policy illustrated through the dividend payout ratio. Company size is the value that indicates the size of a company. According to Hilmi, Utari, and Ali (2008) The size of a company can be assessed in several aspects. The size of a company can be based on the total value of assets, total sales, market capitalization, number of workers, and so on. The greater the assets of a company, the greater the capital invested, the greater the total sales of a company, the more money turnover, and the greater the market capitalization, the greater the company is known to the public. Large, well-established companies will find it easier to obtain capital in the capital market compared to smaller companies. Because the ease of access means that large companies have greater flexibility as well.

Based on this description, it can be seen that companies with larger sizes have greater access to get funding from various sources, to obtain loans from creditors will be easier because large-size companies have a greater probability of winning the competition or surviving in the industry. Company size is a value that indicates the size of a company. Basically, the company is only divided into 3 categories, namely large companies, medium companies, and small companies. Large size companies tend to have bigger agency problems because monitoring is more difficult. The size of the company can be expressed in total assets, sales, and market capitalization. The company that has total assets, sales, and market capitalization, the larger the size of the company. Large companies have many stakeholders. Therefore, the larger the company, the greater the disclosure of information to meet the needs of stakeholders Amran et al., (2009).

Macroeconomic analysis is an analysis of external factors that are macro, in the form of events that occur outside the company, so it cannot be controlled directly by the company. The macroeconomic environment will affect the company's operations in this case the decision making policies relating to the financial performance of banks. The factors that influence a banking company management decision are internal and external factors. Internal factors can be related to the policymaking and operational strategies of the bank. While external factors (factors originating from outside the company), include monetary policy, exchange rate fluctuations, and inflation rates, interest rate volatility, and financial instrument innovations (Siamat, 2005).

Corporate governance is simply a system that regulates how a company is run and monitored. Good Corporate Governance (GCG) is used to ensure that companies set appropriate targets and subsequently implement a system and structure of good corporate governance (GCG) to realize these targets. In addition, good corporate governance (GCG) is also used to provide opportunities for various parties both inside and outside the company to control and monitor the activities of the company and its managers (Rankin et al. (2012). Good corporate governance (GCG) is needed because the structure of the company itself means that those who provide capital for the company do not manage the company directly, they must depend on managers to manage their capital, the separate functions of the manager and owner of a company cause many issues and problems related to corporate governance. interests or also commonly referred to as agency problems will arise when the management of a company is separate from its ownership Good corporate governance can be defined as the structure, system, and process used by corporate organs as an effort to provide added value to the company in a sustainable manner. n in the long run (IICG, 2010).

According to the 2001 Corporate Governance in Indonesia (FCGI) Forum, the definition of Good Corporate Governance is a set of rules governing the relationship between shareholders, managers (managers) of the company, creditors, government, employees and other internal and external stakeholders relating to rights and their obligations or in other words a system that regulates controlling the company. GCG spurs the formation of professional, transparent, clean, and sustainable management patterns. General Guidelines for Good Corporate Governance in Indonesia in 2006 compiled by the National Committee on Governance Policy mentioned five principles of GCG, namely: transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence, and fairness.

Company value is the investor's perception of the company, which is often associated with stock prices. High stock prices make the value of the company is also high. Stock prices are prices that occur when shares are traded on the capital market. Increasing company value is an achievement of company performance results in accordance with the wishes of its owners because with increasing company value, the welfare of the owners will also increase so maximizing company value is very important for a company. According to Keown (2001), the value of the company is the market value of the debt securities and corporate equity in circulation. Enterprise value (EV) or also known as firm value is an important concept for investors because it is an indicator for the market to assess the company as a whole. A company is an organization that combines and organizes various resources with the aim of producing goods and or services for sale Salvatore (2005).

The main purpose of the company according to the theory of the firm is to maximize the company's wealth or value (value of the firm) (Salvatore, 2005). High stock prices make the value of the company is also high. High company value will make the market believe not only in the company's current performance but also in the company's future prospects. Company value is the growing value for shareholders, the value of the company will be reflected in the market price of its shares. Company value can provide maximum shareholder prosperity if the company's share price increases. The higher the share price, the higher the

shareholder prosperity. To achieve the value of the company in general, investors leave their management to professionals.

3. Research Methods

This study will try to analyze the effect of the Asset Structure, Capital Structure, Company Size, Macroeconomics, Risk Management and Profitability on Company Value with Good Corporate Governance (GCG), as a Moderation Variable. The research will be conducted with a quantitative approach where data analysis is quantitative or statistical in order to test the hypotheses that have been set. In order to get the data analysis to be reliable, quantitative techniques will be complemented by qualitative analysis techniques that utilize observations and results of previous studies.

This research will be conducted in Indonesia and the concentration of the research is specific to finance companies in Indonesia. The population in this study are all finance companies in Indonesia and listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Considering that the population of this study has known criteria and characteristics and is not homogeneous, sampling is used purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique based on certain criteria found in the respondents and is considered worthy of representing the population.

The sample in this study is a finance company listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the period 2013 to 2018. The data obtained were then processed by descriptive statistical data using SPSS version 20, and structural equation modeling analysis using Smart-PLS version 3.0. The data obtained are secondary data from finance company financial statements, data from the Indonesia Stock Exchange website, Bank Indonesia, and the Central Statistics Agency. The research model used is as follows:

Figure 1. Research Model

Further data analysis uses Smart-PLS version 3.0, to analyze structural equation models. In the structural equation model analysis consists of two stages, namely the outer model analysis and inner model analysis. In the outer model analysis, the validity and reliability tests are performed. For testing the validity of the loading factor values used with a range of values of 0.5 (Latan and Ghazali, 2012).

Table 1. Validity test

Indicator	Outer Loadings	Indicator	Outer Loadings
SAK	1.000	ROA	0.979
CR	1.000	ROE	0.986
MCAP	1.000	BV	1.000
INF	0.873	Outsider Director	0.775
RATE	0.945	Shareholder	0.835
NPL	1.000		

In the discriminant validity test, the Communality value is used, for reference, the Communality value for all variables is a range of values of 0.5 so that all variables used in the study can be said to meet the validity requirements. The results of the discriminant validity test are as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity Test

Variable	Communality	Variable	Communality
GCG	0.649	Risk Management * GCG	0.996
Macroeconomics	0.828	Asset Structure	1.000
Profitability	0.964	Capital Structure	1.000
Profitability * GCG	0.955	Company Size	1.000
Risk Management	1.000	Value of The Firm	1.000

For further processing of the reliability test and composite reliability test, the reliability testing uses the reference composite reliability value of 0.6. The composite reliability test results are as follows:

Table 3. Composite Reliability Test

Variable	Composite Reliability	Variable	Composite Reliability
GCG	0.787	Risk Management * GCG	0.998
Macroeconomics	0.906	Asset Structure	1.000
Profitability	0.982	Capital Structure	1.000
Profitability * GCG	0.989	Company Size	1.000
Risk Management	1.000	Value of The Firm	1.000

Based on the value of the results of data processing in the outer model analysis, the indicators, and variables used in the study meet the criteria of validity and reliability. In the inner model analysis, the path coefficient and significance are tested. Discussion of the coefficient of determination (R²), predictive Relevance test (Q²), and discussion of hypotheses proposed in the study.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model Analysis

In the determination coefficient test or R^2 , the number 0.670 is obtained, which means the variables used in the study are the Asset Structure, Capital Structure, Company Size, Macroeconomics, Risk Management, Profitability, and Corporate Governance can affect the variable Company Value of 67.0% and the rest influenced by other factors that exist outside the study.

Table 4. Inner Model Analysis

Variable	R – Square	Communitiy	Goodness of Fit (GOF)	Q – Square Predictive Relevance
Value of The Firm	0,670	1,000	0,590	0,803
Profitability	0,111	0,964		
Risk Management	0,330	1,000		
GCG		0,649		
Macroeconomics		0,828		
Profitability * GCG		0,955		
Risk Management * GCG		0,996		
Asset Structure		1,000		
Capital Structure		1,000		
Company Size		1,000		

Overall fit index measurement on the inner model uses the goodness of fit (GOF) test. The GOF value is used for evaluation measurements on the overall research model. The GOF measurement value with a value of 0.10 can be interpreted that the evaluation of the measurement of the overall research model has a low value. Measurement of the GOF value of 0.25 means that the evaluation of the overall research model measurement has a moderate value. GOF measurement of 0.36 can be interpreted that the evaluation of the overall research model measurement has a high value (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The results of data processing according to table 4.5 obtained a Goodness of Fit (GOF) value of 0.590, thus the conclusion from the evaluation of the measurement of the overall research model has a high value.

In the Q-Square Predictive Relevance test, the measurement of Q-square value is performed, to show the level of predictive relevance in a research model. A Q-square value of 0.02 has a weak relevant predictive level, a value of 0.15 has a moderate relevant predictive level, and a value of 0.35 means that the research model has a strong predictive relevance level (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). The results of data processing according to table 5 obtained a Q-square value of 0.803 so that the research model was concluded to have a

high predictive relevance value. In testing the path coefficient and the level of significance obtained results according to table 5 as follows:

Table 5. Path Coefficients and Significance

Relationship Between Variables		Original Sample	T Statistics	Effect and Significance
H1	Asset Structure -> Risk Management	0.007	0.393	Positive is not significant
H2	Asset Structure -> Profitability	0.001	0.120	Positive is not significant
H3	Asset Structure -> Value of The Firm	-0.153	10.230	Significant negative
H4	Capital Structure -> Risk Management	-0.282	9.784	Significant negative
H5	Capital Structure -> Profitability	0.093	3.454	Significant positive
H6	Capital Structure -> Value of The Firm	0.359	12.556	Significant positive
H7	Company Size -> Risk Management	0.598	23.514	Significant positive
H8	Company Size -> Profitability	0.250	9.435	Significant positive
H9	Company Size -> Value of The Firm	0.658	15.316	Significant positive
H10	Macroeconomics -> Risk Management	0.029	1.4214	Positive is not significant
H11	Macroeconomics -> Profitability	-0.151	5.190	Significant negative
H12	Macroeconomics -> Value of The Firm	0.175	7.741	Significant positive
H13	Risk Management -> Profitability	-0.060	4.382	Significant negative
H14	Risk Management -> Value of The Firm	1.550	6.751	Significant positive
H15	Profitability -> Value of The Firm	0.482	4.014	Significant positive
H16	GCG -> Value of The Firm	0.249	9.406	Significant positive
H17	Profitability * GCG -> Value of The Firm	-0.525	3.690	Significant negative
H18	Risk Management * GCG -> Value of The Firm	-1.743	6.795	Significant negative

4. Research Results

4.1 Effect of asset structure on risk management

Asset structure has a positive and not significant effect on risk management. Financial managers in making a funding decision need to carefully consider the benefits and risks of the source of funds to be chosen. Assets are all resources owned by the company to be used in company activities. Companies generally have two types of assets, namely current assets and fixed assets that make up the structure of assets. Subramanyam and Wild (2009) suggest that free cash flow in companies shows an additional effect on investment or the release of investment in operating assets, the availability of free cash flow in the company shows funds that can be used as debt payments or returns to shareholders. The asset structure has a positive and not significant effect on profitability. Companies use fixed assets to produce raw materials into finished goods, so it is important for companies to properly manage fixed assets and current assets in generating profits. The results of the research are in line with a study conducted by Al Ani and Jamil (2015) which examined the effect of asset structure, namely fixed assets and current assets, on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Oman.

Asset structure is measured by the turnover of fixed assets and turnover of current assets while financial performance is measured by return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). The research concludes that the structure of assets does not have a strong influence on profitability.

The asset structure has a negative and significant effect on firm value. Companies with the right portfolio of assets tend to take advantage of investment opportunities well. A financially stable company has a high investment value in terms of fixed assets. The assets owned by the company are used to grow the value of the company. The results support the research conducted by Nyamasege et al. (2014) relating to the effect of capital structure on firm value through asset structure, concludes that assets form the basis of investor confidence to lend funds to a company, the greater the company's assets will guarantee the recovery of capital provided by investors, the asset structure determines the value of a company.

Capital structure has a negative and significant effect on risk management. Next Gobert (2001) examines the impact of capital structure on the optimality of a company's contingent financial contract. The role of financial relations is not only to provide funds but also offers the company protection from risks through contingent financial transfers. Capital structure affects the company's risk management, this is because of the greater the capital owned by the company, the better protection of financial risk. Capital structure has a positive and significant effect on profitability. Good selection and use of capital are some of the key elements of a company's financial strategy. The use of capital structure is an important decision in a company, this is because the profitability of a company is directly affected by the capital structure decision. This study supports a study conducted by Velnampy and Niresh (2012) who investigated the relationship between capital structure and profitability in banks in Sri Lanka, the results of the analysis showed that there is a relationship between capital structure and profitability.

Furthermore, the results of the study show that 89% of total assets in the banking sector are represented by debt and the results of this study can provide advice to banks, creditors, and policy planners to formulate better policy decisions related to capital structure. Companies need to pay attention to the ideal proportion of debt and equity that can affect the value of the company, as well as the level of profitability that can be obtained. Capital structure has a positive and significant effect on firm value. The results of the study are in line with previous studies conducted by Chowdhury and Chowdhury (2010) who tested the effect of debt-equity structure on the value of shares in companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) and Chittagong Stock Exchange (CSE) Bangladesh. The results show that maximizing shareholder value requires a good combination of debt and equity, while the cost of capital has a negative correlation in this decision and must be as minimal as possible. Determination of the composition of a company's capital structure can increase the value of the company on the Exchange. The results of the study provide policy implications for financial managers, in utilizing debt to form an optimal capital structure to maximize shareholder value.

Company size has a positive and significant effect on risk management. The results support previous research conducted by Ali, Shah, & Jan (2015) conducting a study of the impact of ownership structure and company size on operational risk management in the context of Islamic banks on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. The results of the study are an increase in the size of Islamic banks tends to reduce the capital surplus maintained by banks to manage operational risk. Second, a significant positive relationship was reported between excess capital needed to manage operational risk and publicly owned Islamic banks. Third, the results are reported to be as strong as the three regression models giving similar results. Company size has a positive and significant effect on profitability. The results of the study support previous research conducted by Isik et al. (2017) How company size increases profitability in manufacturing companies in Turkey. The results showed that the indicator of company size determined by company assets, sales, and a number of companies concerned with positive results and contrary to the profitability of the company is needed with operating profit on assets. The study has conclusions about an amount sufficient to support a linear relationship between firm size and firm profitability.

Company size has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Investors tend to be more interested in companies with a large scale, so large companies tend to have more stable conditions. This stability attracts investors to own shares in the company, and this will cause an increase in stock prices in the capital market. so it can be concluded that company size has an influence on firm value. The results support the research conducted by Bestariningrum (2015) aimed to determine the effect of capital structure and company size on firm value, case studies on companies listed in the LQ-45 index. The results showed that the capital structure

and company size simultaneously had a positive and significant effect on firm value. While partially, company size has a positive and significant effect on firm value.

Macroeconomics of risk management has a positive and not significant effect. The special and sensitive role of banks in the economic system, any shocks, disruptions, and ineffectiveness in the economic system directly affect the performance of banks and financial institutions as well as phenomena such as high inflation and price shocks and price fluctuations in other markets such as currencies will, directly and indirectly, affect bank risk and profitability. Valipour & Vahed (2017) in their research discussed the role of banks as the most important component of financial markets, playing a very important role in the country's economy. Macroeconomics has a negative and significant effect on profitability. The results support previous research conducted by Kanwal and Nadeem (2013) who investigated the impact of macroeconomic variables on the profitability of public commercial banks in Pakistan during 2001-2011. Empirical findings show a strong positive relationship between real interest rates with profitability. Furthermore, real GDP was found to have an insignificant positive effect on ROA, but an insignificant negative impact on ROE. Inflation, on the other hand, has a negative relationship with profitability. Overall, the selected macroeconomic factors were found to have an impact on the income of commercial banks.

Macroeconomics has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Macroeconomic factors are variables that affect the results of an economy on a broader level, macroeconomic factors including interest rates, exchange rates, and GDP growth rates. The results support previous research conducted by Atanda, Asaolu, and Adewale (2015). This study concludes that value creation, measured by EVA, is a function of the previous year's EVA and that inflation rates, interest rates, foreign exchange rates, capital expenditure ratios and developments in the labor market are important macroeconomic factors that must be optimally enhanced to create economic value for the company.

Risk management has a negative and significant effect on profitability. The results of the study are in accordance with previous studies conducted by Olalekan et al. (2018) relates to the effect of financial risk management on the profitability of commercial banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The findings in the study concluded that credit risk revealed a significant negative effect on bank profitability, while capital adequacy risk was also found to have a positive and significant effect on profitability at commercial banks. Risk management has a positive and significant effect on company value. Risk management needs to be applied in a company, research conducted by Anton (2018) by using a sample of companies registered in the country of Romania, it has been found that the adoption of ERM is associated with higher company values. The results of the study provide support for companies to adopt a more integrated and comprehensive risk management system.

Profitability has a positive and significant effect on firm value. The results support previous research conducted by Kodongo, Mokoteli, and Maina (2014) which examined the factors affecting the profitability of companies registered in Kenya. The results show that sales growth and company size are important factors that drive corporate value, and research conducted by Chen and Chen (2011) regarding profitability and leverage on firm value has long been associated with financial decision making. The greater the profitability of the company, the more profit is given, and the higher the value of the company. Profitability has a positive influence on company value.

Corporate governance has a positive and significant effect on company value. Good corporate governance can be achieved if all company executives implement the provisions of good corporate governance (GCG), namely Transparency, Accountability, Accountability, Independence, Equality, and Fairness. The principles of GCG are essentially the same, namely the responsibility of activities that have been entrusted, transparency of information and conditions that are actually observed by the company, equality of treatment for all shareholders and stakeholders, as well as legal responsibilities for management. (Effendi, 2009). Corporate governance has a negative and significant effect on moderating profitability for company value. The results of the study are in line with previous studies conducted by Juma (2010) focusing on the effect of corporate governance as a moderating variable on the relationship between capital structure and firm value, on companies listed on the Nairobi Stock Exchange (NSE). This study found that all corporate governance tools have an influence on firm value and capital structure. Capital structure is one of many instruments that can maintain the efficiency of corporate governance and protect its ability to create value.

Corporate governance has a negative and significant effect on moderating risk management for company value. The corporate governance structure also determines the rights and obligations of various stakeholders,

if the corporate governance mechanism is designed effectively, the company is expected to be effective in the decision-making process. Strong corporate governance can reduce the risk of companies in various domains and can eliminate or reduce the risk of conflicts of interest between stakeholders in a company, especially the agency relationship between management and shareholders. The results support previous research conducted by Namazi and Nia (2017) who tested the role of corporate governance as a moderating variable on the relationship between the life cycle of a company's products and aspects of risk-taking. The study was conducted on 128 companies on the Tehran Stock Exchange, Iran. The results show the relationship between the stage of growth and decline in the company's product life cycle and risk-taking when corporate governance plays a role as a moderating variable.

5. Conclusion

Management of finance companies needs to pay attention to internal factors, namely profitability, risk management, good corporate government, asset structure, capital structure and company size, and external factors, namely macroeconomic indicators such as inflation and interest rates that can affect the value of the firm.

Asset structure and capital structure need to be considered by the finance company management because it can affect the company's profitability and impact on the company's value. A strong asset structure and capital structure will increase the company's ability to increase the value of the company. Economic indicators such as rising inflation and rising interest rates need to be anticipated by finance companies so that profitability is maintained.

The government as a policymaker in the economy needs to pay attention to the rate of inflation and the potential for high-interest rates to increase, this is because inflation rates and rising interest rates can have a negative impact on finance companies. Stable inflation and interest rates can increase the potential for the development of the financing industry in Indonesia.

Researchers can then pay attention and examine companies in the Financial Technology (Fintech) industry, as a growing industry Fintech provides access to finance to various sectors of society with the support of online technology so that it can reach people in various regions.

References:

- i. Al Ani, M. K. S., & Jamil, S. A. (2015). *The effect of corporate citizenship activities (CCAS) on financial performance and market performance: the Omani experience*. *South East European Journal of Economics and Business*, 10(1), 45-54.
- ii. Ali, A., Shah, A., & Jan, F. A. (2015). *Leverage, Ownership Structure and Firm Performance: Evidence from Karachi Stock Exchange*. *Journal of Management Info*, 6(1), 1-19.
- iii. Amran, A., Bin, A. M. R., & Hassan, B. C. H. M. (2009). *Risk reporting. Managerial auditing journal*.
- iv. Anton, S. G. (2018). *The impact of enterprise risk management on firm value: Empirical evidence from romanian non-financial firms*. *Inzinerine Ekonomika-Engineering Economics*, 29(2), 151-157.
- v. Atanda, F. A., Asaolu, T., & Adewale, A. (2015). *Macroeconomic Variables and Value Creation in the Nigerian Quoted Companies*. Atanda FA, Asaolu TO & Oyerinde AA (2015). *Macroeconomic variables and Value Creation in the Nigerian Quoted Companies*. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(6), 252-262.
- vi. Işık, O. (2017). *Determinants of profitability: Evidence from real sector firms listed in Borsa Istanbul*. *Business and Economics Research Journal*, 8(4), 689-698.
- vii. Bestariningrum, N. (2015). *Analyzing The Effect of Capital Structure and Firm Size On Firm Value (Case Study: Company That Listed In Lq-45 Index Period 2010-2014)*. *Periodical Journal of Scientific Efficiency*, 15(4).
- viii. Brealey, R.A, Myers, S.C., and Marcus, J.A., 2009. *Fundamentals of Corporate Financial Management. Volume 1. Fifth Edition*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- ix. Brigham, E. F. dan Gapenski. Louis C. 1996. *Fundamentals of Financial Management, translation of Ali Akbar Yulianto*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
- x. Brigham, E. F dan Houston, J. F. 2006. *Fundamentals of Financial Management. Tenth Edition. Second Book*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

- xi. Chen, L. J., & Chen, S. Y. (2011). *The influence of profitability on firm value with capital structure as the mediator and firm size and industry as moderators*. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 8(3), 121-129.
- xii. Chowdhury, A., and Chowdhury, S.P., (2010) *Impact of Capital Structure on Firm's Value: Evidence from Bangladesh*. *Jurnal BEH-Business and Economic Horizons Volume 3 Issue 3 October 2010*. pp.111-122.
- xiii. Effendi, M. A., 2009. *The Power of Good Corporate Governance: Theory and Implementation*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- xiv. Fainstein, G. and Novikov, I, 2011, *The role of macroeconomic determinants in credit risk measurement in transition country: Estonian example*. *International Journal of Transitions and Innovation Systems 1, no. 2 (2011): 117-137*.
- xv. FCGI (Forum for Corporate Governance in Indonesia). 2001. *Corporate Governance: Corporate governance*. Third Edition. Jakarta.
- xvi. Ghozali, I., & Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Squares, concepts, techniques and applications use the Smart-pls 3.0 program for empirical research*. Semarang: UNDIP Publisher Agency.
- xvii. Gitman, L. J. 2006. *Principles of Managerial Finance*. 12th ed. Pearson Education Inc. United State.
- xviii. Gobert, K. (2001). *Capital Structure and Risk Management (No. 2001s-51)*. CIRANO.
- xix. Hilmi, U. Dan Ali, Syaiful, 2008. *Analysis of Factors Affecting the Timeliness of Submitting Financial Statements*, 1-22.
- xx. IICG (The Indonesian Institute for Corporate Governance). *Annual Research and Rating Program for Corporate Governance Implementation in Indonesia*. November 20, 2013 (10:12).
- xxi. Juma, J. W. A. (2010). *The Moderating Influence of Corporate Governance on The Relationship Between Capital Structure and The Firm Value of Companies Quoted at The Nairobi Stock Exchange*, Doctoral dissertation, School of Business, University of Nairobi.
- xxii. Kanwal, sara., Nadeem, Muhammad. 2013. *The Impact of Macroeconomic Variables on The Profitability of Listed Commercial Banks in Pakistan*. *European Journal of Business and Social Science II (9): 186-201*.
- xxiii. Keown, Arthur J., Scott Jr., David F., Martin John D. and Petty J. William. 2001. *Fundamentals of Financial Management Volume I*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- xxiv. Kodongo, O., Mokoaleli, T. and Maina, L. (2014). *Capital Structure, Profitability and Firm Value: panel evidence of listed firms in Kenya*. MPRA Paper No. 57116.
- xxv. Latan, H., & Ghozali, I. (2012). *Partial Least Square. Smart PLS Concepts, Techniques and Applications*, 2, M3.
- xxvi. Namazi, M., & Hosseini-Nia, S. (2017). *The Moderating Role of Corporate Governance on the Relationship between a Firm's Product Lifecycle and Risk-Taking*. *Asian Journal of Accounting and Governance*, 8, 87-100.
- xxvii. Nyamasege, D., Bichang, W., Nyang, A. S., & Obasi, P. (2014). *Effect of asset structure on value of a firm: a case of companies listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange*. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(7), 205–212.
- xxviii. Olalekan, L. I., Mustapha, L. O., Irom, I. M., & Emily, B. N. (2018) *Corporate Board Size, Risk Management and Financial Performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria*. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research Vol.6, No.1, pp.1-20, January 2018*
- xxix. Rankin, et al. 2012. "Contemporary Issues in Accounting". Queensland: John Wiley & Sons.
- xxx. Rivai, V, 2009. *Human Resource Management For Companies From Theory to Practice*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada
- xxxi. Ross, Stephen, Randolph Westerfield, and Jeffrey Jaffe. *Corporate finance*. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, 2012.
- xxxii. Salvatore, Dominick. 2005. *Managerial Economics Second Book*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- xxxiii. Siamat, D. (2005). *Management of Financial Institutions Fifth Edition*. Jakarta (ID): LPFE UI.
- xxxiv. Valipour, H., & Vahed, M. S. (2017). *Risk Management and Forecasting Macro-Variables Influences on Bank Risk*. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12(6), 137-150.
- xxxv. Velnampy, T., dan J. A. Nires. 2012. *The Relationship between Capital Structure dan Profitability*. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research 12(13)*.

- xxxvi. Weston, J. Fred dan Copeland, Thomas E. 2001. *Financial Management Volume I. 9th Edition.* Jakarta: Binarupa Aksara.
- xxxvii. Wild, J. J., & Subramanyam, K. R. (2009). *Financial Statement Analysis. The USA.*